

PLATFORM STRATEGY OF THE QURAN PLATFORM: A CASE STUDY OF THE DIGITAL QURAN PLATFORM AT SYAAMIL GROUP

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Abstract

This research centers on the substantial repercussions of the decline in Al Quran sales and significant revenue reduction experienced by Syaamil Group in 2022 due to the COVID-19 pandemic. In response to this circumstance, Syaamil Group opted to devise a business innovation strategy by venturing into the domain of digital platforms. This research aims to show pain points from users and includes solutions that the platform can provide. In addition, this research also seeks to establish the market needs and potential competition that the Syaamil Digital Quran platform will face. This qualitative research uses The Platform Innovation Kit, edition 5.0 Loop#1 Discover and Launch, to dissect pertinent data. The study highlights two main elements in the platform business model: problem, solution, and market behavior. The design of the business model platform uses these four elements, whereas the Syaamil Digital Quran Platform highlights three user segments: consumers, producers, and partners. Market behavior highlights the ecosystem in the platform that refers to emerging needs, where the Al Quran Digital Syaamil platform currently focuses on Islamic content, online Quran recitation classes, and portable mushaf. Based on the data processing results, it is concluded that the Syaamil Platform consists of three ecosystems: Quran readers, Syaamil Group itself, payment gateways, content creators, and Quran teachers. In addition, there is a high need from Platform users to get an Al Quran Platform with Al Quran memorization features, online bookstores, Al Quran learning features, digital mushaf, and ease of waqf.

Keywords: Decline Sales of Al Quran; Platform Business Model; Platform Innovation Kit edition 5.0 Loop#; Syaamil Group

1. INTRODUCTION

Covid-19 had a very significant impact on many companies in Indonesia. Sasongko pointed out in an article published in the DJKN of the Ministry of Finance (Sasongko, 2020) that the economic impact caused by Covid-19 will make economic growth slow down. Sosongko (2020) also pointed out that the manufacturing sector was affected by the supply chain of raw materials caused by the scarcity of raw materials, especially from China. The delay in raw materials also led to an increase in product prices and inflation.

A decline also occurred in the publishing industry. An article published on Kumparan.com (*Kondisi Penerbit Buku Makin Memprihatinkan, Penjualan Anjlok 50 Persen | Kumparan.Com*, 2022) said that more than 58.2% of publishers who are members of IKAPI experienced a decrease in turnover of more than 50%. The condition of publishing companies that had begun to falter from before the pandemic was exacerbated by Covid-19. Technological

disruption in terms of digital curiosity has also exacerbated the decline in turnover in the publishing industry.

However, not all industries have experienced a decline due to Covid-19. An article published on Liputan6.com (Liputan6.com, 2022) said that the digital industry is the hope after Covid-19 to restore the economy. Doni Ismanto (Liputan6.com, 2022), the founder of IndoTelkom Forum said in the article that digitalization is a pillar in every business in adapting to the pandemic.

Post Covid-19, many companies have experienced a decline in revenue. Syaamil Group as a company also experienced the impact of declining sales. The significant decline in sales in 2022 made it difficult for Syaamil Group to do business after Covid-19. This research uses a case study of Syaamil Group, which is a Quran publishing company based on data obtained by researchers during the Covid-19 pandemic, physicals Quran sales at Syaamil Group have decreased. The decline amounted to around 1.250.642 copies of the Quran copies in 2022. This data is smaller than 2021 which amounted to 1.792.441 copies, which previously experienced an upward trend from 2019 to 2021.

Fig 1: Syaamil Group Mushaf Sales Chart from 2019-2022

This decline in sales has an impact on the decline in Syaamil Group's turnover, from a good performance in 2020 and 2021 with a turnover of up to Rp. 95,359,016,530, decreasing to Rp. 70,704,154,902 in 2022.

From the decline experienced, the researcher obtained information that Syaamil Group is planning to develop a digital Quran platform as an effort to continue to innovate to create sustainability of the Quran product. However, as a researcher, researchers must compile a platform development plan with scientific methods and data obtained in the field. Thus, the author created the title "Al Quran Platform Development Strategy: Case Study of the Digital Quran Platform at Syaamil Group".

Based on the problem analysis above, the researcher feels that Syaamil Group needs to design a platform development strategy for its current mushaf. With the design of a platform development strategy, it is hoped that Syaamil Group will be better prepared to enter the digital market. In the context of platform development, some processes need to be considered so that the platform can meet the needs of users. There are several processes in determining the features and services of a platform. Based on sources from the Platform Innovation Kit v5.0, there are five phases in developing a platform. Each phase has different tools for determining variables. The tools in question include business model canvas, design thinking, lean startup, growth hacking, to business development.

Fig 2: Platform Innovation Kit Innovation Framework

However, the development of a platform has the biggest challenge, which is how to make the platform meet the needs of users, both in terms of features or services to technological infrastructure. To avoid the risk of a platform being neglected and not used by users, researchers compiled a study to develop a development strategy for the Al Quran platform.

Based on the research title above, the researcher will focus on analyzing and examining what strategies need to be implemented by Syaamil Group regarding the development plan for the Digital Quran Platform. In the research process, researchers will use tools to facilitate the analysis and research process. The tools include platform design toolkits, design thinking, lean startup, and business development. Based on Fig.2, these tools are part of the platform innovation kit v5.0 which comprehensively integrates all tools in one tool. The platform innovation kit consists of several canvases that will help researchers describe in detail the platform development process from the producer, consumer, and partner sides.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Publishing Industry

The history of the modern book began in 1455 with the arrival of Johannes Gutenberg's Forty-Two Line Bible (Tat Keh, 1998). The book publishing business only entered the market in the early 1900s, when the publishing company was only a small business, where researchers had to attend to two different roles in one company, the role of printing and the role of selling. The publishing company experienced a rise in market expansion with the increase in literacy and transformed the printer-bookseller into a modern publishing company (Tat Keh, 1998).

The publishing company industry is evolving as the market continues to grow (Tat Keh, 1998). Organizations also change with the influence of the three major forces listed in the table above, namely technological changes, changes in market desires, and company mergers and acquisitions.

In the publishing industry, technology has played a huge role in the changes. Almost every part of the publishing industry, from writing books to distributing them to consumers, faces technological changes that come in various forms (Tat Keh, 1998).

In addition to technology, consumer needs have also changed. According to Eisenhart (1998), many industry owners are shifting their focus to the people, who have a demand for products and services that meet very diverse and specific needs that match the evolving lifestyles (Tat Keh, 1998).

Although not as influential as technological changes and shifts in demand, the process of merger or acquisition is also a big factor in the publishing industry. A merger or acquisition is an exchange of existing assets (Tat Keh, 1998). In detail, an acquisition is the process of directly purchasing assets or equity of a targeted company, while a merger is the process of combining two or more business entities into one larger business unit (Tat Keh, 1998). With various risks, mergers are usually taken by publishing companies to enlarge their business scope (Tat Keh, 1998).

B. Business Model

The term business model is widely used by companies and in academic literature (Kim, 2015). In academic literature, theory, and practice, especially business models, are mentioned as crucial in building a business strategy. The business model consists of various components such as price, product, distribution, organizational characteristics structure, and market strategy (Kim, 2015). Broadly speaking, a business model can be defined as identifying what consumers need, specifying the technology and organization that will house the business, and capturing value from activities that are important in a business ecosystem (Teece, 2018). Without balance, a business model will not last long, especially for businesses that are already aiming for profit. In other words, a good business model must be able to become a logical bridge for consumers to want to use the services provided by the business (Teece, 2018).

Schon (2018) said that there are several components needed in a business model. A schematic of these components is as follows:

- a. *Value Proposition: Product and Service; Customer Needs; Geography.*
- b. *Revenue Model: Pricing Logic; Channel; Customer Interaction.*
- c. *Cost Model: Core Assets and Capabilities; Core Activities; Partner Network.*

The elements of a business model must be clear and integrated (Teece, 2018). For example, the basic capability of a company is the need to be able to provide planned customer value. In other words, the business model must be able to connect the internal structure and overall management model of a company (Teece, 2018).

A business model translates logic and provides data and other evidence that can show how a business can create value for consumers (Teece, 2010). The business model also shows the financing, revenue, and profit plans associated with the business that can deliver that value (Teece, 2010). The business model explains how the company provides value to consumers, which is then converted into a payment for profit. From profit, innovation will be obtained, which will make the business grow according to consumer needs and existing technology (Teece, 2010).

C. Platform Business Model

A platform business model is a business model where there is a two-sided market, network effect, and business ecosystem (Kim, 2015). Broadly speaking, the platform business model is a business model where there are transactions that occur in two directions (Kim, 2015). Platforms and platform business models are tools that are currently widely used to accelerate the development of business strategies as a place to create an ecosystem, making it easier for companies to create needs and provide supplies to be able to meet the needs expected by the market (Kim, 2015). Iansiti and Levien (Kim, 2015), stated that a platform is a collection of solutions by providing access related to the problems experienced by actors in a business ecosystem. A platform is understood as something that allows participants who are members of the platform ecosystem to build goods, services, or complementary technologies in an integrated technology (Kim, 2015). In the economic focus, a platform consists of three main concepts, namely two-sided market, network effect, and business ecosystem, all of which are key to creating a natural ecosystem. (Kim, 2015).

Two-Sided Market

A two-sided market is an economic platform with multiple actors or stakeholders providing benefits to each other (Kim, 2015). Two-sided markets are usually used to bring together one or more stakeholders who interact using a medium or platform (Kim, 2015). Two-sided markets can be found in many industries, alongside conventional product offerings and services. In general, the market refers to the physical and conceptual space in which consumers and producers exchange transactions. (Kim, 2015). In contrast, the term market in a two-sided market refers to goods or services that provide a physical platform or virtual platform where two or more different groups interact with each other. (Kim, 2015).

Network Effect

The network effect is an economic scale relationship that affects stakeholders that affect the value that will be given to certain products (Kim, 2015; Kim & Yoo, 2019). In other terms, the network effect refers to the need for economies of scale which implies at least some level of interaction relationship with the value of the product or service depending on the number of users (Kim & Yoo, 2019). The network effect requires that the more users who specifically use a product or service, the more valuable the product or service will be to each user (Kim, 2015). The ICT-driven business sector is the sector that benefits most from the network effect and is most affected by the network effect (Kim, 2015).

Business Ecosystem

The business model expresses the logic, data, and other evidence that connects to the value proposition for customers and the revenue and cost structure the company needs to incur to deliver that value (Nurhayati et al., 2020). A business model is a method applied to a business to earn money in its business environment related to earning revenue and generating profit (Fattah et al., 2022).

D. Research Framework

Based on the theory that has been stated, the researcher designed a research framework to examine external factors and internal factors in designing a platform adopted from the business ecosystem model and platform model (Kim & Yoo, 2019), where to be able to define the parameters in the business model, the platform requires external and internal analysis.

Fig 3: Research Framework

The external and internal analysis in this research was then assembled using Platform Innovation Kit v5.0 Loop#1 Discovery and Launch which was designed by Matthias Walter. The stages carried out are grouping and placing the canvas in the appropriate place according to the stages. After performing the above steps, the data obtained was mapped into a business model using Platform Business Model Canvas. The canvases entered are intended for the entry-level stage, where this research is for a platform that has not yet been created. From the results of data processing, the concept of a Platform Business Model for the Syaamil Digital Quran platform is outlined as the basics of determining management strategies to run a predetermined business model.

3. METHODOLOGY

The research method used is a qualitative research method with a case study approach. The use of a case study approach is because researchers describe and analyze the appropriate business model for the AI Quran Digital Platform by considering the needs of the actors that are still not met by the existing AI Quran Digital Platform in the market.

In this study, researchers observed the existing Platform business model, the needs of the actors in the ecosystem that make up the Platform and other influencing external conditions. The results of the research focus on the design of the Digital AI Quran Platform business model to compete with the Digital AI Quran Platform that has already entered the market. The object of research is Syaamil Group, which acts as a provider or owner of the Quran which will later develop into a Digital Quran Platform.

In the analysis section, the data is analyzed using the Platform Innovation Kit version 5.0 Loop#1 Discover and Launch which consists of 12 aspects, where these aspects consist of one or more canvases that have the aim of clarifying these aspects. Each canvas consists of different but interconnected variables and forms a series of business model canvas platforms. The following is an image of the Loop#1 Platform Innovation Kit v.5.0.

The Discover and Launch diagram from Platform Innovation Kit Loop#1, describes a business strategy consisting of 4 parts, namely problems, and solutions, market behavior, business concept, and platform organization. For this reason, each of the contents contained in Platform Innovation Kit Loop#1 is used as part of the canvas to design the platform business model canvas.

All research processes and data used in this study, especially for data that is primary and not intended for the public, have received approval from the authorities, both from Syaamil Group as the company used as the object of this research, as well as the actors involved as sources whose data are included in this study. In terms of secondary data collection, researchers took sources from the internet to collect data on external conditions that would later affect the platform. In terms of primary data collection, in addition to documents, researchers conducted interviews with several groups of people according to the needs of the Digital Quran Platform ecosystem.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Al Quran Digital Platform Ecosystem

The ecosystem of Syaamil Group's Digital Quran Platform shows that this platform has a business model that involves various parties, such as users, Quran teachers, content creators, and Payment Gateway. This is in line with research that discusses platform business models, which has similar results to (Afrizal & Tricahyono, 2023) which examines the business model of crowdfunding platforms. The platform business model is a business concept that involves various parties in a digital platform that facilitates interaction between service providers and recipients (Wahyuningtyas et al., 2021). In Syaamil Group's platform ecosystem, the platform's business model involves several parties, such as users, Quran teachers, content creators, and Payment Gateway. Users are very important parties in the ecosystem of Syaamil Group's Digital Quran Platform. Users are the main beneficiaries of the content, features, and services provided by Syaamil Group's Digital Quran Platform. Users can access tafsir, translations, and religious education content that can help them understand the teachings of the Quran better. In addition, features such as prayer time notifications and Qibla direction can also help users in carrying out religious obligations. In Syaamil Group's Digital Quran Platform ecosystem, the user is the center of the ecosystem. This means that users are the main focus in the development and provision of content, features, and services provided by the platform. (Nurbaiti & Mariah, 2020) discusses the influence of attitudes towards e-books and physical books on people's interest in reading in the industrial era 4.0, which also highlights the role of users in adopting digital technology.

Syaamil Group's Digital Quran Platform allows users to interact with Quran teachers, content creators, and fellow users to share insights and experiences. This interactive feature allows users to deepen their understanding of the Quran's teachings and expand their social network (Afrizal & Tricahyono, 2023). Quran teachers play an important role in the ecosystem of Syaamil Group's Digital Quran Platform. Wahyuningtyas et al, (2021) discussed the role of teachers in creating a competitive model for cooperatives in the digital age. Koranic teachers provide interpretations, lessons, and deep insights into Quranic verses. Through this platform, Quran teachers can share their knowledge in the form of videos or interactive learning materials. Collaboration with Quran teachers can also improve the quality of content and provide more comprehensive guidance to users. With the interaction feature, Quran teachers can communicate directly with users, answer questions, and provide guidance. Content Creators have an important role in enriching digital Quran content. In the Syaamil Group Digital Quran Platform ecosystem, content creators can contribute to providing quality and useful content for users. These contents can be in the form of interpretations, translations, and religious education content that can help users understand the teachings of the Quran better. In addition, content creators can also provide diverse perspectives and encourage users to interact more actively with the content (Spjeldnæs & Karlsen, 2022). Platform developers must pay attention to the needs and desires of content creators in the development and provision of content, features, and services provided by the platform (Kim et al., 2021). With the collaboration between content creators and platform developers, it is expected that users can

easily access the Quran, gain a better understanding of its contents, and contribute to expanding access to Quran content for the wider community. Therefore, the role of content creators is very important in enriching digital Quran content and ensuring that the content provided by the platform can be useful for users. Payment Gateway plays a vital role in enabling secure and efficient financial transactions on Syaamil Group's digital Quran Platform. Payment Gateway is a service that facilitates online transactions with a secure infrastructure. Payment Gateway enables easy transfer of funds and validates payment information provided by customers. In Syaamil Group's digital Quran Platform ecosystem, the Payment Gateway allows users to make premium content payments, subscribe to online Quran classes, and use various payment methods such as credit cards, bank transfers, e-wallets, and others (Chen & Granitz, 2012). Payment Gateway offers a solution to make transactions on Syaamil Group's digital Quran Platform more secure. Payment Gateway has an automated system that processes payment transactions online and authorizes various payment processes, whether banking, credit card, bank transfer, or directly from consumers. The multiple security systems on the Payment Gateway ensure that transactions are carried out securely and protect users' financial information (Lai & Chang, 2011).

Payment Gateway facilitates the payment process in Syaamil Group's digital Quran Platform ecosystem. With the Payment Gateway, users can make payments quickly and easily through various payment methods provided. This minimizes obstacles in the payment process and increases user convenience in transactions (Dennstedt & H, 2016). Liao & Liu (2023) discuss the integration of technology and marketing to increase e-book consumption. Although this study does not specifically discuss Payment Gateway, it shows the importance of digital technology in facilitating transactions and increasing the consumption of digital products such as e-books. In Syaamil Group's Digital Quran Platform ecosystem, Payment Gateway plays a role in facilitating payment transactions for digital content provided by the platform. With the Payment Gateway, users can easily and safely make financial transactions on Syaamil Group's Digital Quran Platform. Payment Gateway plays an important role in ensuring the smoothness and security of transactions, as well as increasing user convenience in transactions.

The platform business model in the Syaamil Digital Quran Platform ecosystem can be an example of various types of digital businesses that develop by utilizing digital technology and facilitating interactions between service providers and recipients. Several parties need to work together on the partner side, including payment gateway providers, Quran content contributors, educational and religious institutions, and technology developers. The payment gateway provider acts as a payment service provider so that Platform users can transact with various payment options (Chen & Granitz, 2012). Quran content contributors are individuals or groups who support the platform by providing Quran content, such as translations, tafsir, and other supporting materials. Educational and religious institutions can collaborate in providing Quran-related guides and learning resources. Technology developers are responsible for developing and maintaining the technical infrastructure of the digital Quran Platform. With a well-coordinated digital Quran Platform ecosystem, it is expected that users can easily access the Quran, gain a better understanding of its contents, and contribute to expanding access to Quran content for the wider community. The formation of the Syaamil Digital Quran Platform

business ecosystem after becoming a Platform is certainly larger than the current business ecosystem.

Fig 4:1 Platform Ecosystem

B. Platform Business Model

Fig 5: 2Business Ecosystem Al Quran Platform

The five elements of the business model based on the research that has been carried out with comparison to previous business models can be described, including:

a. Problems and Solutions

Syaamil Digital Quran Platform is a business platform that has three user segments, namely consumers, producers, and partners. The consumers of the Syaamil Group Digital Quran Platform are male and female Muslim users with an age range of 13-45 years. According to Lai

& Chang (Lai & Chang, 2011) and Liao & Liu (Liao & Liu, 2023), this reflects a fairly broad and diversified potential consumer, by research on the use of e-books and digital content in the literature. In addition, the Producer segment of the Syaamil Group Digital Quran Platform is Syaamil Group. While the partners of the Syaamil Group Digital Quran Platform are Quran teachers, content creators, and Payment Gateways. The service users of the Syaamil Group Digital AI Quran Platform are those listed in the value creation on the Business Model Canvas Platform.

b. Market Behaviour

Market Behavior reflects on canvases such as Platform USP Canvas, Ecosystem Forces Scan Canvas, and Longtail Discovery Canvas. Emerging Needs expressed in the Ecosystem Forces Scan Canvas in the Syaamil Digital Quran Platform currently focus on Islamic content, online Quran recitation classes, and mushaf. Core services owned by the Syaamil Digital Quran Platform include the Quran memorization feature, Islamic product store, learning to read feature, digital mushaf, waqf, ease of using the application, recitation teacher, and recitation community. This core service helps and supports users to learn to be good and disciplined Muslims. These services reflect research that states that digital content can influence consumer reading behavior (Nurhayati et al., 2020).

5. CONCLUSIONS

Based on an in-depth analysis of the ecosystem development and business model of Syaamil Group's digital Quran platform, the following conclusions are obtained:

- a. Syaamil's Digital Platform can provide a solution for Indonesian Muslims aged 14-45 who have difficulty accessing the Quran anywhere. The diverse conditions of Quran consumers in Indonesia can be facilitated by Syaamil Group's Digital Platform. Syaamil Group is a company entering the ecosystem as a producer since all the content will be provided by Syaamil Group. Payment Gateway, Content Creator, and Quranic Teacher will be entering the platform ecosystem as a partner that will heighten the core value propositions of the AI Quran Digital Platform.
- b. There is a high need for the Digital Quran Platform which is expressed by the consumer's need for Islamic content, online Quran recitation classes, and easy-to-carry mushaf. Platform's core values that must be provided are the Quran memorization feature, an online bookstore, learning to read the Quran feature, digital mushaf, ease of waqf Quran, and teachers who can teach the Quran to people who want to learn the Quran.

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